

Banach Fixed Point Theorem and Applications

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Abstract

The main objective of this research paper is to study the applications of the Banach fixed point theory. First we mention the definitions of contraction mapping, statement and proof of Banach fixed point theorem. Then we illustrate fixed point of α -real valued functions, α -matrix equations and α -integral equations with examples.

Introduction

Let $f: X \rightarrow X$ be a mapping from a set X to itself. We call a point $x \in X$ a fixed point of f if $f(x) = x$. For example, if $[a, b]$ is a closed interval then any continuous function $f: [a, b] \rightarrow [a, b]$ has at least one fixed point. This is a consequence of the intermediate value theorem, as follows. Since $f(a) \geq a$ and $f(b) \leq b$, we have $f(b) - b \leq 0 \leq f(a) - a$. The difference $f(x) - x$ is continuous, so by the intermediate value theorem 0 is a value of $f(x) - x$ for some $x \in [a, b]$, and that x is a fixed point of f . Of course, there could be more than one fixed point.

Banach Fixed Point Theorem

In this section we shall introduce the definitions of metric space, fixed point, contraction mapping and existence and uniqueness theorem of fixed point in a complete metric space.

1.1 Definition. A set X , whose elements we shall call points, is said to be a *metric space* if with any two points p and q of X there is associated a real number $d(p, q)$ called the distance from p to q , such that

- (1) $d(p, q) > 0$ for $p \neq q$ and $d(p, p) = 0$;
- (2) $d(p, q) = d(q, p)$;
- (3) $d(p, q) \leq d(p, r) + d(r, q)$, for any $r \in X$.

1.2 Definition. Let (X, d) be a metric space. A sequence $\{x_n\}$ is a *Cauchy sequence* if for all $\varepsilon > 0$ there is an $n_\varepsilon \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $n \geq n_\varepsilon, m \geq n_\varepsilon$ implies $d(x_n, x_m) < \varepsilon$.

1.3 Definition. A metric space (X, d) is *complete* if every Cauchy sequence in X converges in X .

1.4 Definition. Let (X, d) be a metric space. A mapping $T: X \rightarrow X$ is a *contracting mapping*, or *contraction*, if there exists a constant $0 \leq \alpha < 1$, such that $d(T(x), T(y)) \leq \alpha d(x, y)$ for all $x, y \in X$, α is called the *contractivity factor* of T .

1.5 Definition. Let $T: X \rightarrow X$ be a map of a metric space to itself. A point $x \in X$ is called a *fixed point* of T if $T(x) = x$.

For example, let X be the two-element set $\{a, b\}$. The function $f: X \rightarrow X$ defined by $f(a) = b, f(b) = a$ has no fixed point, but the other three functions that map X into itself each have one or two fixed points.

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1.6 Theorem Let $T: X \rightarrow X$ be a contracting mapping with factor α on a complete metric space (X, d) . Then T has precisely one fixed point $u \in X$. Furthermore, for any $x \in X$, the sequence $T^k(x)_{k=0}^{\infty}$, where $T^k = T \circ T \circ \dots \circ T$ (k times) converges and $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} T^k(x) = u$.

Proof: Fix $x \in X$. We first show that the sequence $T^k(x)_{k=0}^{\infty}$ is Cauchy with respect to the metric d . Note that $T^k x = T(T^{k-1}x)$ for any $k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, $k \geq 1$. Let $n \geq m > 0$ be nonnegative integers. Then by induction, we see that

$$d(T^n x, T^m x) = d(T(T^{n-1}x), T(T^{m-1}x)) \leq \alpha d(T^{n-1}x, T^{m-1}x) \leq \alpha^m d(x, T^{n-m}x).$$

By the triangle inequality, we have

$$d(x, T^{n-m}x) \leq \sum_{k=1}^{n-m} d(T^{k-1}x, T^k x) \text{ which implies that}$$

$$\begin{aligned} d(T^n x, T^m x) &\leq \alpha^m \sum_{k=1}^{n-m} d(T^{k-1}x, T^k x) \\ &\leq \alpha^m \sum_{k=1}^{n-m} \alpha^{k-1} d(x, Tx) \\ &= d(x, Tx) \sum_{k=1}^{n-m} \alpha^{k+m-1} \\ &= \alpha^m d(x, Tx) \frac{1 - \alpha^{n-m-1}}{1 - \alpha}. \end{aligned}$$

It follows that $d(T^n x, T^m x) \rightarrow 0$ as $m \rightarrow \infty$.

Since (X, d) is complete, there exists $u \in X$ such that $T^k x \rightarrow u$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$.

We now show that $Tu = u$. Since T is continuous,

$$\begin{aligned} Tu - u &= T\left(\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} T^k x\right) - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} T^k x \\ &= \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} T^{k+1} x - \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} T^k x \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $Tu = u$.

We now show uniqueness, suppose $v \in X$ satisfies $Tv = v$.

We have that $d(u, v) = d(Tv, Tu)$ and for contraction T we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(Tv, Tu) &\leq \alpha d(v, u), \quad 0 \leq \alpha < 1, \\ d(v, u) &\leq \alpha d(v, u) \end{aligned}$$

$$(1 - \alpha) d(v, u) \leq 0, \quad (1 - \alpha) \neq 0$$

$$d(v, u) = 0$$

$$v = u.$$

2. Fixed Point of Real Valued Functions

Consider the metric space (X, d) where $X = \mathbb{R}$ and $d = | \cdot |$ is the Euclidean distance. Let $[a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}$ and let $\phi : [a, b] \rightarrow [a, b]$ be a differentiable function satisfying $\|\phi'\|_{L^\infty} \leq k < 1$, k is called Lipschitz constant.

We seek a solution of the equation $\phi(x) = x$. For any $x, s \in [a, b]$, we have by the mean value theorem that there exists $t \in (x, s)$ such that $\phi(x) - \phi(s) = \phi'(t)(x - s)$.

$$\text{Thus } |\phi(x) - \phi(s)| = |\phi'(t)| |x - s| \leq k |x - s|.$$

This implies that ϕ is a contraction mapping with factor bounded by $k < 1$.

By theorem 1.6, there exists a unique solution $x^* \in [a, b]$ such that $\phi(x^*) = x^*$.

2.1 Theorem: Every contraction mapping is continuous.

Proof: Let $T: X \rightarrow X$ be a contraction on a metric space (X, d) , with modulus β and let $\bar{x} \in X$. Let $\epsilon > 0$ and choose $\delta = \epsilon$ then $d(x, \bar{x}) < \delta \Rightarrow d(Tx, T\bar{x}) \leq \beta \delta < \epsilon$.

Therefore T is continuous at $\bar{x}$. Since $\bar{x}$ was arbitrary, T is continuous on X . The above proof actually establishes that a contraction mapping is uniformly continuous.

As a first application of the contraction mapping theorem, we consider the solution of an equation $f(x) = 0$. One way to obtain a solution is to recast the equation in the form of a fixed point equation $x = Tx$, and then construct approximations x_n starting from an initial guess x_0 by the iteration scheme

$$(1) \quad x_{n+1} = T x_n.$$

There are many ways to rewritten an equation $f(x) = 0$ as a fixed point problem, some of which will work better than others. Ideally, we would like to rewrite the equation as a fixed point equation in which T is a contraction on the whole space, or at least a contraction on some set that contains the solution we seek.

To provide a simple illustration of these ideas, we prove the convergence of an algorithm to compute square roots. If $a > 0$, then $x = \sqrt{a}$ is the positive solution of the equation $x^2 - a = 0$.

We rewrite this equation as the fixed point problem

$$(2) \quad x = \frac{1}{2} \left(x + \frac{a}{x} \right).$$

The associated iteration scheme is then

$$(3) \quad x_{n+1} = \frac{1}{2} \left(x_n + \frac{a}{x_n} \right),$$

corresponding to a map $T: (0, \infty) \rightarrow (0, \infty)$ given by

$$(4) \quad Tx = \frac{1}{2} \left(x + \frac{a}{x} \right).$$

Clearly, $x = \sqrt{a}$ is a fixed point of T . Moreover, given an approximation x_n of $\sqrt{a}$, the average of x_n and $\frac{a}{x_n}$ should be a better approximation provided that x_n is not too small, so it

is reasonable to expect that the sequence of approximations obtained by iteration of the fixed point equation converges to $\sqrt{a}$. We will prove that this is indeed true by finding an interval on which T is a contraction with respect to the usual absolute value metric on $\mathbb{R}$.

First, let us see whether T contracts at all points, For $x_1, x_2 > 0$, we estimate that

$$\begin{aligned} |Tx_1 - Tx_2| &= \left| \frac{1}{2} \left(x_1 + \frac{a}{x_1} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left(x_2 + \frac{a}{x_2} \right) \right| \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left| 1 - \frac{a}{x_1 x_2} \right| |x_1 - x_2|. \end{aligned}$$

It follows that T contracts distances when $3x_1 x_2 > a$. To satisfy this condition we need to exclude arguments x that are too small. Therefore, we consider the action of T on an interval of the form $[b, \infty)$ with $b > 0$. This is a complete metric space because $[b, \infty)$ is closed subset of $\mathbb{R}$ and $\mathbb{R}$ is complete.

In order to make a good choice for b we first observe that

$$(5) \quad Tx = \sqrt{a} + \frac{(x-a)^2}{2x} \geq \sqrt{a}$$

for all $x > 0$. Therefore, the restriction of T to $[\sqrt{a}, \infty)$ is well-defined, since

$$T([\sqrt{a}, \infty)) \subset [\sqrt{a}, \infty),$$

And T is a contraction on $[\sqrt{a}, \infty)$ with $c = \frac{1}{2}$. It follows that for any $x_0 \geq \sqrt{a}$, the sequence $x_n = T^n x_0$ converges to $\sqrt{a}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Moreover, the convergence is exponentially fast, with

$$\begin{aligned} |T^n x_0 - \sqrt{a}| &\leq |T^n x_0 - T^m x_0| \\ &\leq \frac{c^n}{1-c} |Tx_0 - x_0| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2^{n-1}} \left| \frac{a}{x_0} - x_0 \right|. \end{aligned}$$

If $0 < x_0 < \sqrt{a}$, then $x_1 > \sqrt{a}$ and subsequent iterates remain in $[\sqrt{a}, \infty)$, so the iterates converge for any starting guess $x_0 \in (0, \infty)$.

2.2 Example. To find the real solution of the equation $x^3 + x - 1 = 0$ by iteration method. Let $f(x) = x^3 + x - 1$, we guess that the real root lies in the interval $(0, 1)$ because $f(0) < 0$ and $f(1) > 0$. Here is the iteration formula

$$x_{n+1} = \phi(x_n); n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Case (i) If we write the given equation $x = 1 - x^3 = \phi(x)$, say $|\phi'(x_n)| = |-3x^2| = 3x^2$.

$$\text{Let } x_0 = 0.6 \text{ then } |\phi'(x_0)| = 3(0.6)^2 = 1.08 > 1.$$

Thus $\phi(x_n) = 1 - x_n^3$ does not converge to the solution near 0.6.

Case (ii) If we rewrite the equation as $x(1 + x^2) = 1$ then let $x = \frac{1}{1 + x^2} = \phi(x)$.

$$|\phi'(x)| = \left| \frac{-2x}{(1 + x^2)^2} \right|$$

For the initial point $x_0 = 0.6$, we have $|\phi'(x_0)| = \frac{2(0.6)}{(1 + 0.6^2)^2} = 0.649 < 1$.

Thus the iteration process, $x_{n+1} = \frac{1}{1 + x_n^2}$, $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, converges as follows:

$x_0 = 0.6, x_1 = 0.73529, x_2 = 0.64907, \dots \dots, x_{26} = 0.682327, x_{27} = 0.682328, x_{28} = 0.682328$.
 Thus, the real solution of $x^3 + x - 1 = 0$ corrected to 6 significant figures is $x = 0.682328$.

Remark: Note that the definition of a fixed point requires no structure on either the set X or the function T .

3. Matrix Equations

Consider system of linear algebraic equation given by the matrix problem $Ax = b$, where

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & \dots & a_{nn} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)^T \text{ and } b = (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n)^T.$$

We can rewrite this system of equations as

$$x_1 = (1 - a_{11})x_1 - a_{12}x_2 - \dots - a_{1n}x_n + b_1$$

$$x_2 = -a_{21}x_1 + (1 - a_{22})x_2 - \dots - a_{2n}x_n + b_2$$

$$\dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots$$

$$x_n = -a_{n1}x_1 - a_{n2}x_2 - \dots - a_{nn}x_n + b_n$$

For $1 \leq i, j \leq n$, set $\alpha_{ij} = \delta_{ij} - a_{ij}$, where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta function. We can write the above system of n equations as

$$x_i = \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_{ij} x_j + b_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

We see that the matrix problem $Ax = b$, or $x = x - Ax + b$, is equivalent to finding fixed point of the map T such that $Tx = (I - A)x + b$. Observe that, for $x, x' \in \mathbb{R}^n$, then

$$\begin{aligned} Tx - Tx' &= (x - Ax + b) - (x' - Ax' + b) \\ &= (x - x') - (Ax - Ax') \\ &= (I - A)(x - x'). \end{aligned}$$

We claim that $Ax = b$ has a unique solution if $\sum_{j=1}^n |\alpha_{ij}| \leq k < 1, \forall i = 1, \dots, n$.

We define a metric d on $\mathbb{R}^n$ by $d(y, y') = \sup_{1 \leq i \leq n} |y_i - y'_i|$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Then } d(Tx, Tx') &= \sup_{1 \leq i \leq n} \left| \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_{ij} (x_j - x'_j) \right| \\
 &\leq \sup_{1 \leq i \leq n} \sum_{j=1}^n |\alpha_{ij}| |x_j - x'_j| \\
 &\leq \sup_{1 \leq i \leq n} \left(\sum_{j=1}^n |\alpha_{ij}| \right) \left(\sup_{1 \leq i \leq n} |x_j - x'_j| \right) \\
 &= \left[\sup_{1 \leq i \leq n} \sum_{j=1}^n |\alpha_{ij}| \right] d(x, x')
 \end{aligned}$$

$$d(Tx, Tx') \leq k d(x, x')$$

which shows that T is a contraction mapping.

This is an application of Theorem 1.6 in $\mathbb{R}^n$.

4. Integral Equations

4.1 Theorem: (Fubini) If $f(x, y)$ is $X \times Y$ integrable, meaning that it is measurable and $\int_{X \times Y} |f(x, y)| d(x, y) < \infty$, then

$$\int_X \left(\int_Y f(x, y) dy \right) dx = \int_Y \left(\int_X f(x, y) dx \right) dy = \int_{X \times Y} f(x, y) d(x, y).$$

4.2 Definition: Let $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$ with $p, q > 1$. Then Holder’s inequality for integrals states that

$$\int_a^b |f(x)g(x)| dx \leq \left[\int_a^b |f(x)|^p dx \right]^{\frac{1}{p}} \left[\int_a^b |g(x)|^q dx \right]^{\frac{1}{q}}$$

with equality when $|g(x)| = c|f(x)|^{p-1}$.

If $p = q = 2$, this inequality becomes Schwarz inequality

$$\int_a^b |f(x)g(x)| dx \leq \left[\int_a^b |f(x)|^2 dx \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\int_a^b |g(x)|^2 dx \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \text{ where } |g(x)| = c|f(x)|.$$

Similarly, Holder’s inequality for sums states that

$$\sum_{k=1}^n |a_k b_k| \leq \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |a_k|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |b_k|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}$$

with inequality when

$$|b_k| = c |a_k|^{p-1}$$

If $p = q = 2$, this becomes Cauchy’s inequality

$$\sum_{k=1}^n |a_k b_k| \leq \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |a_k|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n |b_k|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \text{where } |b_k| = c |a_k|.$$

4.3 Theorem: Let $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ with $a < b$. let $(x, y) \mapsto K(x, y)$ be a measurable function on $\{a \leq x \leq b, a \leq y \leq b\}$. Suppose that $\int_a^b \int_a^b |K(x, y)|^2 dx dy < \infty$ and $g \in L^2([a, b])$.

Then the integral equation $f(x) = g(x) + \mu \int_a^b K(x, y) f(y) dy$ has a unique solution for $|\mu| < \frac{1}{\|K\|_{L^2([a, b] \times [a, b])}}$.

Proof: We claim that the function h defined by

$$h(x) = g(x) + \mu \int_a^b K(x, y) f(y) dy \text{ where } f \in L^2([a, b]).$$

By linearity, the triangle inequality, and our hypothesis that $g \in L^2([a, b])$, we only need to show that $\psi(x) = \int_a^b K(x, y) f(y) dy \in L^2([a, b])$.

By Fubini’s theorem and Holder’s inequality, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_a^b |\psi(x)|^2 dx &\leq \int_a^b \left(\int_a^b |K(x, y)| |f(y)| dy \right)^2 dx \\ &\leq \int_a^b \left(\int_a^b |K(x, y)|^2 dy \right) \left(\int_a^b |f(y)|^2 dy \right) dx \\ &= \left(\int_a^b \int_a^b |K(x, y)|^2 dy dx \right) \left(\int_a^b |f(y)|^2 dy \right) < \infty . \end{aligned}$$

Define a mapping $T: L^2([a, b]) \rightarrow L^2([a, b])$ by $Tf = h$, where the metric d is the standard L^2 metric. For $f_1, f_2 \in L^2([a, b])$, we have by Holder’s inequality that

$$\begin{aligned}
d(Tf_1, Tf_2) &= \left| \mu \left| \int_a^b \int_a^b K(x, y) (f_1(y) - f_2(y)) dy \right|^2 dx \right|^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
&\leq \left| \mu \left| \int_a^b \int_a^b |K(x, y)| |f_1(y) - f_2(y)| dy \right|^2 dx \right|^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
&\leq \left| \mu \left| \int_a^b \int_a^b |K(x, y)|^2 dy \right| \left| \int_a^b |f_1(y) - f_2(y)|^2 dy \right| dx \right|^{\frac{1}{2}} \\
&= \left| \mu \left| \int_a^b \int_a^b |K(x, y)|^2 dy dx \right|^{\frac{1}{2}} d(f_1, f_2) \right. \\
&= |\mu| \|k\|_{L^2([a, b] \times [a, b])} d(f_1, f_2).
\end{aligned}$$

If $|\mu| < \frac{1}{\|K\|_{L^2([a, b] \times [a, b])}}$, then the preceding estimate shows that T is a contraction mapping.

Applying theorem 1.6 completes the proof.

Conclusion

When $f: X \rightarrow X$ is a contraction with constant c , any iterate f^n is a contraction with constant c^n ; the unique fixed point of f will also be the unique fixed point of any f^n . If X is any set (not yet a metric space), $c \in (0, 1)$, and $f: X \rightarrow X$ is a function such that each iterate $f^n: X \rightarrow X$ has a unique fixed point then there is a metric on X making it a complete metric space such that, for this metric, f is a contraction with contraction constant c .

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